

**Building a Strong Bridge - A Critical Policy Analysis of Droichead:
Ireland's Integrated Professional Induction Framework for Teachers**

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Few professions place as much pressure on their newest recruits as teaching. Newly-qualified teachers differ from members of other professions, such as medicine and law; there is no equivalent of residency or devilling that newly-qualified doctors or barristers must undertake as part of their early professional learning. Newly-qualified teachers enter their classrooms with full professional responsibility, yet they have encountered inadequate mentoring, lack of support and excessive responsibilities which are not commensurate to their teaching experience. Research indicates that the learning needs of newly-qualified teachers must be met to shape their future engagement with professional learning. Enter Droichead, Ireland's formalised teacher induction programme; since July 2020, it is the sole route of entry into the teaching profession in Ireland. Using Bowe, Ball and Gold's policy cycle framework and focusing on primary education, this paper offers a critical policy analysis of Droichead and identifies future policy trajectories in the area of teacher induction. Its recommendations include the need for increased professional learning opportunities for experienced teachers to effectively mentor newly-qualified teachers, consistency in feedback language to newly-qualified teachers, and how the Inspectorate might be engaged as an independent agent in this non-evaluative induction process.

Keywords: Newly-Qualified Teachers; Teacher Induction; Mentoring; Professional Learning; Ireland.

Three key highlights

- Newly-qualified teachers are expected to take full professional responsibility upon entering the classroom upon graduation.
- International studies recognise that newly-qualified teachers require specific supports to help them adjust to their new roles.
- This critical policy analysis of Droichead identifies that while the design of Ireland's teacher induction programme incorporates international best-practice, there is still potential for its development.

Introduction

Pre-formalised induction, newly-qualified teachers were “thrown in at the deep end and left to sink or swim” (Coolahan, 2003). Droichead aims to remedy this; a non-evaluative induction process, it is under the remit of the Teaching Council (TC) and it “support[s] the professional learning of newly-qualified teachers during their induction phase” (TC, 2017, p. 3). Introduced in 2013 as a pilot programme across 123 primary and post-primary schools (Smyth et al, 2016), since 2020, Droichead is the only route for teacher induction. To work in state-funded recognised schools, teachers must be registered with the TC. Upon completing this induction process, teachers qualify for full-registration with the TC. Replacing the previous evaluative Inspectorate-led teacher probation process, Droichead (the Irish word for bridge) is one of the TC’s Continuum of Teacher Education’s three elements and it is the link between the other two; Céim: Standards for Initial Teacher Education and Cosán: Framework for Teachers’ Learning.

There are two strands to the Droichead process. Strand A is school-based and newly-qualified teachers (NQTs) are supported by the members of the school’s Professional Support Team (PST); mentoring, portfolio-based Professional Learning (PL) and classroom observation are key features of Droichead and the PST guides and facilitates this. Strand B consists of additional PL activities; these include compulsory attendance at cluster meetings in local education centres and at least one other PL activity, based on the agreed individual needs of the NQT (TE, 2017). Droichead is delivered via the National Induction Programme for Teachers (NIPT), which is also under the remit of the TC.

Theoretical Perspectives

In Ireland, the term NQT describes teachers in the first five years of their teaching career. In Australia, terms such as ‘neophyte’ and ‘beginner teachers’ are used (Kearney,

2013; Spooner-Lane, 2017). The United Kingdom also uses the term ‘NQT’, along with ‘early-career teachers’. Regardless of the terms used, research indicates that post-graduation, NQTs require specific supports. In early studies, problems with “discipline”, “classroom methods” and “motivation” (Dropkin & Taylor, 1963) are reported. In the 1980s, McDonald observed that the issues faced by NQTs are almost identical, regardless of the country where the study was undertaken. Hargreaves (1994, 2000) adds isolation to the challenges faced by NQTs, underscoring the issues discussed by Dropkin and Taylor in the 1960s. In more recent studies, NQTs have named inadequate mentoring and supervision, behaviour management challenges and excessive responsibilities as common concerns (McCormack & Thomas, 2003; Killeavy, 2006).

Hence, the international trend towards providing targeted NQT induction programmes.

Induction programmes exist to transform an NQT into a competent professional

(Schlechty; 1985, Kearney, 2013). Banks *et al.* identify the hoped-for impacts of teacher induction; teachers’ engagement with teaching, student achievement and teacher retention (2015). While mentoring is a key element of teacher induction, it is only one feature.

Kearney (2014) presents the nine features of successful induction policies on a global level and these features are set out in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Main features of successful induction policies globally.

Droichead addresses all nine features and the PST plays a role across all of these. An interesting aspect of the PST is its non-hierarchical make-up; while the principal or deputy principal is typically a PST member, they are equal-status participants. The non-evaluative nature of Droichead is a key feature; this lends it well to many of the features as identified above by Kearney, especially those of mentor support, collaboration and opportunities for PL, both for NQTs and their mentoring colleagues.

NQT Induction Policy

Ball *et al.* observe that “teachers do not think about, perceive and act towards policy in particular ways in local circumstances but they are not simply autonomous and transparent social subjects” (2011, p. 612). While NQTs are subject to government policy via Droichead, in-school arrangements determine the type and level of support that NQTs receive, not the policy itself. Lipsky’s ‘street-level bureaucrats’ come to mind as policy is interpreted on the ground by those who enact it (1980) and that policy is subject to “interpretations of interpretations” (Rizvi and Kemmis, 1987, p. 14). In the case of Droichead, the members of the PST are the “street-level bureaucrats”; those who interpret and enact this induction policy for the benefit of the NQTs it is designed to serve.

When analysing a national or international policy, it is important to locate its broad context (Taylor, 1997); not only to provide an analysis of its objectives but also an interrogation of the political and economic factors that drive the policy’s formulation. Performing a critical policy analysis helps uncover not only a policy’s efficacy but can also identify its possible trajectories and future development. Bowe, Ball and Gold’s (1992) policy cycle provides a theoretical framework for analysing education policy as a process rather than an end-product. It requires researchers to trace "policy formulation, struggle, and response from within the state itself through to the various recipients of

policy" (Ball, 1993b, p. 16). Furthermore, it interrogates whether policy is interpreted as intended. Lastly, it acknowledges practitioners' agency within the context of practice and not merely as recipients of policy. As stated by Bowe, Ball and Gold, "practitioners do not confront policy texts as naïve readers, they come with histories, with experiences, with values and purposes of their own" (1992, p. 22). Given the centrality of the PST in NQT induction, the context of practice (described below) is where the effectiveness of Droichead is truly road-tested. This framework takes a poststructuralist stance; this is a theoretical perspective that emerged in the 1960s and 1970s in France and has since spread to other fields and countries. It challenges traditional notions of language, knowledge, power, and identity by emphasising the role of discourse, difference, and contingency in shaping social reality. Poststructuralists argue that meaning is not fixed or objective but rather constructed through language and social practices.

Policy Analysis Framework

A 'continuous' policy cycle, Bowe, Ball and Gold's policy analysis framework consists of three non-linear primary policy contexts:

- *The context of influence*: where public policy is initiated and constructed, where global and national trends and interests emerge alongside the prevailing ideological, economic, and political conditions of the jurisdiction in which the policy was formulated. It also helps reveal the interest groups who influence policy as well any pre-dating policy evolutions that influence the policy.
- *The context of text production*: somewhat related to the context of influence, this is where policy texts are articulated in the language of public good and common sense. It explores the why, when, and where of policy text construction. While it takes into account the interests of relevant stakeholders and those whose interests

the policy is designed to serve, it also considers those voices that are missing and any possible hidden agendas. It explores the policy's key concepts, format, language, and accessibility to its intended audience and issues of funding and evaluation.

- *The context of practice*: relating to policy implementation and where the consequences of policy are experienced, it explores who can access the policy and who does so, as well as how open the policy is to interpretation by practitioners. It also considers resistance to the policy as it is implemented, any unintended consequences and the identification of any winners or losers (Bowe, Ball and Gold, 1992; Vidovich, 2001).

Context of Influence

The early-nineties was a period of major reform in teacher education in Ireland. The Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development's (OECD) 1991 Review of Education in Ireland, the Green Paper: Education for a Changing World, (Department of Education, 1992) and the White Paper: Charting our Education Future (Department of Education, 1995) all emphasise the quality of teacher education, teaching and learning, and the capacity of the teaching profession to meet society's needs. One key outcome was a recommendation for a "reconceptualisation" of initial teacher education (ITE) and towards a continuum of teacher education and career-long PL. The early 2000s was another period of reform relating to teacher PL with the establishment of the TC in 2006; its key purpose is to "promote teaching as a profession" and "to maintain and improve the quality of teaching in the state" (Government of Ireland, 2001, p. 1). Teacher induction was addressed by the Department of Education and Skills (DES) Inspectorate in their 2005 report on educational disadvantage. Some concerns were flagged, specifically that the

majority of teachers interviewed stated that their ITE programmes did not prepare them for the challenges of teaching in disadvantaged settings. Almost one-third of the teachers had three years' teaching experience or less.

2011 saw the roll-out of the National Strategy: Literacy and Numeracy for Life (LNS) 2011-2020 (DES, 2011). The Inspectorate found that student teachers did not have sufficient time within the Bachelor of Education and Postgraduate programmes to develop certain skills and knowledge, specifically relating to numeracy (DES, 2005). As a result, both undergraduate and postgraduate ITE programmes were extended to create four-year Bachelor Education and two-year Primary Masters in Education programmes. The initial Droichead Policy was published by the TC in 2013 in advance of the 2013-2016 pilot scheme. The Economic and Social Research Institute's (ESRI) 2016 review of Droichead echoes the Inspectorate's 2005 DEIS report; principals felt that NQTs were not sufficiently prepared to work with children and families from diverse backgrounds. The current Droichead framework was published in 2017. Revisions continue to be made to the framework in response to the needs of NQTs, schools and wider societal needs.

Context of Text Production

While policies are usually understood to be in the 'public good', Bell and Stevenson state that "educational issues are [...] are usually presented as problems requiring a technical solution" (2016, p. 146). Bowe, Ball and Gold's policy framework sees this context of production as based upon "popular (and populist) common sense and reason" (1992, p. 20). The role of the media within this context is key; those who are to benefit from policies are often only made aware of them through the media. The agendas of media producers are inherently influential on disseminated messages and these are, in turn, influenced by the dominant voices in society (McLuhan, 1964; McQuail, 1994). The

context of text production is not only influenced by the political landscape in which the policy text is developed but also by the expected reception it will receive by those who it impacts. Droichead's policy text is quite brief at four and a half pages long. The language used is accessible for its intended audience; the text is directive, instructive and it clearly states the purpose of the policy.

Reference has been made to the context of influence and the different pre-existing policies and legislation before Droichead. However, there are unheard voices within this context of text production. While the Department of Education, the TC and the OECD are identified as the strong players in the context of influence, the opinions of those who enact policy in schools in Ireland are largely missing from this context; it has largely stayed within the same realm as the stakeholders who influenced the policy. Reflecting global trends in teacher induction during a period of over two decades, Droichead was developed to meet international standards of integrated induction/mentoring programmes. The establishment of the TC (and NIPT) predates this but its genesis can be seen in the OECD's 1991 report. The ESRI's 2016 Droichead pilot review acknowledges that volunteering schools had a high percentage of principals who had been mentored upon commencing their roles. These schools also had formalised NQT induction processes. The self-selecting nature of this pilot scheme suggests that it appealed to school leaders who felt they had the necessary leadership capacity and staff enthusiasm to commit to this considerable shift in NQT induction. This is opposed to the findings of the Irish Primary Principals' Network's (IPPN) 2015 survey of principals who had not engaged with the Droichead pilot; "not everyone would be suited to this role (PST) and the very people who may be interested may not have the skills to do it well" (IPPN, 2018, p. 4). This leads to the context of practice; where the rubber of policy hits the road.

Context of Practice

“Policies are crude and simple. Practice is sophisticated, contingent, complex and unstable’ (Ball, 1995, p. 10). Vidovic cements Ball’s definition of policy as a turning point in policy analysis as it conceives “policy as a whole process to incorporate its initial construction as well as subsequent practices which may bear little resemblance to the original intent” (2007, p. 285). Droichead’s success is determined by how it is interpreted by those who implement it. It hinges on follow-through by the PST, those who are the interpreters and actors in the implementation of this teacher induction programme. The most recent Droichead Quality Assurance (QA) Report (TC, 2022) indicates an overall satisfaction with Droichead but some questions exist around the role PSTs play and the Inspectorate’s absence within this formative non-evaluative NQT probation space. This does not sit completely easy with schools; the 2022 QA report calls for a standardised feedback language framework and also for a level of Inspectorate-led oversight. This indicates that there is an on-the-ground desire for a level of Inspectorate involvement in probation that existed pre-Droichead. Kearney (2014) identifies opportunities for observation as one of the main features of a successful induction programme, however, another area identified within the 2022 QA report are limited opportunities for classroom observation by NQTs and PST members due to ongoing shortage of substitute teachers.

Conclusion of Analysis and Potential Policy Trajectory

Having conducted this policy cycle analysis of Droichead, the following conclusions are made. Firstly, international literature addressing NQT early-career experiences indicates the need for effective teacher induction programmes. Droichead meets these standards and cannot be deemed merely as unconsidered ‘policy borrowing’, whereby an organisation or jurisdiction copies and pastes another’s to fill a lacuna in

practice. Rather, it considers an appropriate symbiosis in culture, practice and application (Phillips and Ochs, 2004). It meets the recommendations that Conway *et al.* (2009) and Kearney (2013, 2014) make regarding a fit-for-purpose induction programme for NQTs. Secondly, while Droichead meets international standards to induct teachers into a community of practice, this analysis has uncovered addressable areas. For example, some schools may explicitly assign a PST role to teachers who have salaried extra duties but not every school has this option. Thirdly, while PST members receive PL, its focus is on the process of Droichead itself and not on the development of mentoring skills. Finally, as addressed earlier, there is also a need for consistency in feedback language and also for the potential for a role for the Inspectorate.

This analysis identifies three key areas for exploration in any future remodelling of Droichead. The first relates to who watches the watchmen? In the case of a school that may have employed an NQT who requires more support than the PSTs or school leadership teams can offer or who simply is not suited to the job of teaching, that school cannot 'fail' the NQT's induction. It is yet to be tested in a legal setting how such a situation would be dealt with should it arise. The QA Report of 2022 raised this as a possible role that the Inspectorate might fill in the future. However, this should also be approached with caution as it could serve to be counterproductive to carve away at the professional judgement of experienced teachers and PST members.

The sustainability of Droichead's non-evaluative nature is one that may be challenged in future. The rise of accountability and performativity in teaching on the international stage (Sachs, 2016; Cochrane-Smith, 2021; Mockler, 2022) cannot be ignored in this context. The scope of this minor paper is not broad enough to explore the marketisation of education and increasing neo-liberalism in Government spaces in other

jurisdictions to discuss the possible signposts of the eradication of teacher's professional autonomy but it warrants further attention.

Finally, as described earlier, both the DES Inspectorate (2005) and the ESRI (2016) identified principals' concerns that NQTs were not sufficiently prepared to work with children and parents from diverse backgrounds. While the need for this has been addressed in the Graduate Teacher Standards in Céim: Standards for Initial Education (TC, 2020), this is a relatively recent development. This recognised skills and knowledge gap may also be addressed through PL for NQTs via the NIPT as they undertake Droichead.

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